

BANGLADESHI MIGRANT PARENTS' INVOLVEMENT IN THEIR CHILDREN'S SCHOOLING: IDENTIFYING THE BARRIERS

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Abstract

*Existing researches widely recognise the significance of parental participation in children's schooling. Many of these distinguish barriers of involving migrant parents as a crucial factor in children's education. Previous studies suggest that in UK, teachers, schools and education policy have explicit expectations of parents to participate and implicitly consider them as a **homogenous group**. However, Bangladeshi migrant parents living in UK, whose own educational experiences are different from their children's, are likely to have a very different set of assumptions about schooling and their own participation.*

This study focused on identifying factors that might bar migrant parents' participation in their children's schooling. By adopting a qualitative approach this study looks into parent's socio-economic and educational background, their experience as a migrant parent of school going children and their views about participation with their child's school activity. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with Bangladeshi migrant parents living in the London Borough of Newham. Using those data the paper analyses the barriers that Bangladeshi parents experience in participating in school activities.

Findings of the study suggest that parents' educational background influence their views and their ways of participating in children's education. A number of factors are found to be inhibiting their participation in children's schooling. These include language barrier, lack of knowledge about the UK education system, socio-economic status of the migrants, and student-parent relationships. The study suggests some areas of improvement to ensure an inclusive schooling experience for the migrant children. In addition, future research possibilities are mentioned.

Keywords: Home-school partnership, Barriers, Immigrant, Parenting, Inclusion

Introduction

In 1978, Warnock Report first made way for the integrated education system in England (Hodkinson, 2010). Inclusive education was then defined as the teaching of disabled and non-disabled children in the same school, although Hodkinson criticised the word 'disabled' as 'patronising and degrading'. Even in the literature, inclusive education is mainly focused on the participation of children with physical and mental disabilities. However, Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special Needs Education (UNESCO, 1994) expanded its scope to include children from different minority ethnic groups and stated that-

'Schools should accommodate all children regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic or other conditions. This should include disabled and gifted children, street and working children from remote or nomadic populations, children from linguistic, ethnic or cultural minorities and children from other disadvantaged or marginalized areas or groups.' (UNESCO, 1994, p. 15)

UK is currently a signatory to a number of international conventions and statements, including Salamanca Statement (Runswick-Cole, 2011). However, literature regarding inclusive schooling and education of minority ethnic children in UK is not extensive. Existing literatures show substantial attention to parents with disabled children whereas minority ethnic parents are largely overlooked. As parental involvement is considered as greatly facilitative to inclusive education (Palmer, Fuller, Arora, & Nelson, 2001), it seems reasonable that when parents have positive attitudes towards participating in their children's schooling, teacher and school staff will also be more inclined to realise inclusion.

To welcome social diversity arising from gender, nationality, race, language of origin, social background, level of educational achievement or disability (Mittler, 2000) and defining individual needs, inclusive education system is to ensure that schools are for all. To achieve full participation of all children in an inclusive school, Mittler (2000) stressed upon 'concerted effort' not only by teachers and school staff, but also by parents and families of the children as well. Parental participation in the school is crucial in this regard. Hence, acquiring knowledge about minority ethnic children and their parents' participation in the education could be useful in developing awareness of this issue.

Evidence of the importance of parental participation in schools in Britain first appeared in the Plowden Report (DES, 1967). Since then, different policies have emphasised parental participation. Among them, some of the most significant are the 1997 Government White Paper 'Excellence in Schools' (DfEE, 1998) and the Home-School Agreement Policy (DfEE, 1998). To improve achievement of the pupils, several researchers have also emphasised on parental participation in school (Brooker, 2002; Crozier & Davies, 2007; Desforges & Abouchar, 2003; Harris & Goodall, 2007; Siraj-Blatchford, 2010). However, there remain some clear gaps between the policy and the reality. The reality depicts a different scenario for the working class and minority ethnic parents (such as Bangladeshi and Pakistani parents), who are often considered as 'hard to reach' by the practitioners, (Crozier and Davies, 2007). Researchers defined this 'hard to reach' parents as parents 'who are deemed to inhabit the fringes of school, or society as a whole- who are socially excluded' (Crozier and Davies, 2007). Parents considered as such are more likely to be excluded from being the most important part of their children's schooling and education. In these circumstances, exploring the barriers parents face in participating in their children's schooling might be informative for future policy formulate.

What is Parental Participation?

Parental participation does not have any universal definition (DCSF, 2009). However, as the purpose of this study is to identify barriers of participating- both at home and in school, the following definition might be useful,

Parental participation means –
“ ‘good parenting’ in the home pre-school (which provides a good foundation of skills, values, attitudes and self-concept); visits to school to gather relevant information and establish good relationships; discussions with teachers to keep abreast of the child's progress or to discuss emergent problems; and assisting more broadly in the practical activities and governance of the school.” (Desforges and Abouchar, 2003, p. 7)

At home parental participation

It is now widely recognized that parental participation has a powerful impact on children's attainment and achievement and “at home good parenting” is especially significant even after other factors that affect success in schooling have been taken out of the equation (Desforges and Abouchar, 2003). In its various forms- for instance, helping with homework (Desforges and Abouchar, 2003); creating an effective learning environment (DCSF,

2009); home discussion and home supervision (Sui-Chu & Willms, 1996), etc - parental participation plays a significant role in children's attainment.

In school parental participation

Parents' involvement in school is also emphasised by several researchers (e.g. Siraj-Blatchford, 2010, Crozier and Davies, 2007, Brooker, 2002, Desforges and Abouchaar, 2003, Harris and Goodall, 2007). According to DCSF (2009), parents are the prime educators before starting school who also have a major influence on children's education in school life and beyond. In addition, a number of researchers have found positive relationships between parental involvement and student achievement through parent-teacher combined work which could also improve school attendance (Harris and Goodall, 2007). Parental involvement could influence students' through increased attendance as well since separate researchers have found a strong relationship between attendance and attainment (Sheppard, 2009). Epstein (1995) describes the benefits of in school parental participation as-

'(parental participation) can improve school programmes and school climate, provide family services and support, increase parents skills and leadership, connect families with others in the school and in the community, and help teachers with their work..' (Epstein, 1995, p. 701)

Parents' in school participation can be regarded as a two-way communication, where one side is the parents and the other side is the teachers and the school. Harris and Goodall (2007) argued that if the schools have beliefs that 'parents matter', they need to make a two-way relationship with parents, based on mutual trust, respect and a commitment for the betterment of children's achievement. Blair et al. (1998) viewed this communication as listening to and learning from students and their parents, then re-appraising and adapting school practices accordingly. Nonetheless, there is a clear gap between what is said and what is done in the name of parental participation in England, particularly for the ethnic minority parents. Ethnic minority parents are often regarded as working in a different value system (Page, Whitting, & Mclean, 2007), because of their diverse educational backgrounds, language barriers and lack of knowledge about the education system and so on. Thus minority ethnic parents might experience exclusion because of the barriers they face in participating from the school, teachers as well as from the policy initiatives.

Significance of the study:

As discussed above, it is crucial to rethink about the policy in regards to parental participation in school activity since it helps children's achievements. To create equal provision for participation, needs of all types of parents regardless of their background needs to be addressed. Bangladeshis are the fourth top nationals among the migrants in London (The Immigration Observatory, 2014) and similar statistics could be found for other areas of England as well. To ensure equal participation of Bangladeshi migrant parents in the home-school partnership it is important to identify the barriers they experience in this regard so that actions could be incorporated in future policies to remove those.

Objectives

The objective of this study is to identify the barriers that are experienced by the Bangladeshi migrant parents in London to participate in their children's home and school activities.

Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative approach to attain its objectives. A semi-structured interview was used to elicit data from minority parents on how they participate in their children's education and what barriers they face. The

interview schedule was developed with help of previous researches that focuses on constraints of home-school relationships.

The interview questions were clustered in three different areas. Among them, the first cluster focuses on parent factors including their educational and cultural background, language barriers, knowledge of the education system and their expectation. School factors are focused in the next one that includes agenda on the expectation of teachers and schools' and teachers' professionalism. Finally, policy factors are grouped in order to discuss the policy initiatives in the national and school level that impede participation.

All the interviews were in Bengali and were tape recorded. Later they were transcribed and translated to English.

To select the participants of this study, a convenient sampling method was adopted and ten Bangladeshi migrant parents (mostly mothers since they are more involved in parenting than fathers) were selected for collecting data. However, different socio-economic background was a criterion of selecting samples since there might be different views and experience among them and we tried to bring as much details from different backgrounds as possible.

Findings and Discussion

Findings are described under three main themes namely: parent factors, school factors and policy factor. Verbatim excerpts from the transcripts are also used to provide more details to the reader. Respondents' occupational background and gender is mentioned when quoted so that their socio-economic background can be related with their response.

1. Parent Factors: Parent factors are related with respondents' personal background which has influence on the home-school relation.

1.1 Settling down in a new country

All the respondents, in various ways, expressed their struggles in establishing themselves in a new country that affected their relationships with children's education and schooling. Among them, male respondents were more explicit in expressing their views in this regard. Occupations of the respondents are mentioned because it could be related with their struggles in settling down..

'I didn't know the standard of what I am supposed to expect from the school, we were new then.....' (Male, Businessman)

'As it was a primary stage [for choosing school] and we just came into this country, we had to focus on our own establishment first. So we chose... [school's name] school' (Male, Lecturer)

'I was pregnant. My husband was an international student... I did not work for last three years, because I have to take care of my kid....so mainly because of our work schedule, we could not give enough time in his schooling....'
(Female, A fast food shop Trainee Manager)

Establishing oneself in a new country is often a matter of concern and respondents in this study also identified that they prioritised concern for establishment rather than engaging themselves with children's education. But one respondent revealed that after settling down, he concentrated on his children's education and made their education a priority.

‘Now I have a full time job... and I try to give as much time as possible for my children’s education. But seven years ago, I could not afford to give 4-5 hours to my children everyday’ (Male, Lecturer)

Migrant parents consider their migration as an opportunity to change their economic status. Moreover, parents who have arrived in the country recently are more concerned about their immigration status and livelihood than any other issues. Data also revealed that parents seem not adequately aware about the information about the schools. However, once establish themselves, they become comparatively more concerned about their children’s future.

1.2 Knowledge and understanding of the education system

The knowledge barrier was also one of the biggest challenges mentioned by the majority of the respondents.

‘I don’t know anything about this education system’ (Female, A shoe outlet worker)

‘We just came into this country; we have to look for our own establishment first. Also the education system here is different than what we had back home. We have to learn about the schooling first’ (Male, lecturer)

Respondents frequently demonstrated their trust in the school system, but their lack of clarity of the ways in which school operates, for instance, homework policy, teacher-parent meeting policy, school choice policy are a concern for them. Though according to DfES (2005), every parent should be able to access information working with teachers to enable their children achieves their full potential, that does not seem to be the case here. One respondent mentioned,

‘I wanted to know more about the education system, but it was not always possible to discuss things with the teachers. In case of parent’s evening, it was normally held 4 times a year. In case of parent-teacher meeting, say there are 30 children. When their parents come to that meeting, teacher have to divide their time among all parents, they have a set of time, 10 to 15 minutes. He cannot give you hours; he cannot show you all the papers and things like that if he even wishes to. They have policy; they follow it.... I want to say that it is actually ‘something is better than nothing’... (Female, A shoe outlet worker)

Earlier researches also mentions that helping children in a new country is a major concern in ethnic communities (Datta, 2000). Gregory (2008) indicated, with reference to the ethnic minority parents about reading in a new language that-

‘When parents understand what schools are doing...parents are more likely to support rather than resist what schools are doing.’ (Gregory, 2008 p. 107)

Although the schools’ white paper under the previous government prioritised the importance of personalised learning and teaching for individual needs of all pupils, especially minority ethnic groups, it is also identified that many parents are not sure what they are expected to do by schools or how to relate to schools (DfES, 2005). Respondents in this study also showed a strong relationship between knowledge of education system and their ability and confidence to support their children’s education and school.

However, two female respondents expressed a positive attitude to overcoming their limited knowledge of the education system to achieve success for their children.

‘When my first child was in the school, I volunteered (at a school) for almost two years.... I wanted to know more about how I need to take care of.... [herchild’s name]’s education...’ (Female, Housewife)

1.3 Language Barriers

From the interviews it was apparent that migrant parents' language is one of the major barriers to effectively maintain communication with the school. Data suggest that, female parents are more concerned in this regard than male. Language was indicated as a barrier by five female respondents. On the other hand, none of the male respondents mentioned about language as a barrier to communicate with schools and teachers. Here the occupation of the parents are mentioned which could indicate the language skill level.

'As my English is not very good, his father takes care of his reading, and I take care of his homework' (Female, A fast food shop Trainee manager)

In addition, there was a strong sense of retaining community culture and language in the majority of the respondents. In terms of language, seven respondents mentioned using solely Bengali at home.

'Home language is Bengali, standard Bengali. Even Kids are also asked to use Bengali at home, nothing else.' (Male, Lecturer)

'This language (Bengali) is our root. So I don't want my child to forget their language' (Female, a shoe shop employee)

However, three respondents have adopted a mixed approach to communicate with children.

'First language is Bengali and the second language is English for my daughter' (Male, International Student)

The reason behind using Bengali language is the belief that it may remind them about their roots. None of the respondents used English language exclusively at home, though a few of them infrequently used English with their children.

Studies of Bangladeshi mothers carried out in Tower Hamlets by ILEA in 1985 also found mother's priority of retaining a cultural, religious and a linguistic identity through their children, but they also wanted their children to be a part of the wider society (Tomlinson & Hutchison, 1991).

Though Tomlinson and Hutchison (1991) have not found any direct relationship between parents' knowledge of English and children's school performance, fluency in English can have an impact on reading and writing that does affect children's education and their communication with schools and teachers. Furthermore, Cummins and Scheker (2003) identified that bilingualism has a positive effect on cognitive development. However, Martin-Jones and Jones (2000) pointed out that parents are sometimes assumed as 'illiterate' if they cannot read or write English. Respondents in this study also referred to their language barrier in a way that affects their communication with teacher and school activities.

1.4 Cultural Background

Cultural background plays a crucial role in shaping parents' views toward education and ways of participation in their children's schools as illustrated, for instance, by the South Asian parents in Crozier and Davies's study (2007) or the Chinese parents and pupils in Francis and Archer's study (2005). Roy (1999) depicted the South Asian educational tradition where parents send their children to the teacher's house (called 'Guru') to be taught by the

Guru. Parents have the utmost trust on the Guru and these traditional values can still have an influence. Pratt (1994) and Holden, Desforges and Hughes (1996) have also found similar trust of professional educators and teachers by the South Asian parents who assume teachers would know what is best for their children.

One of the respondents in this study said,

“Teacher knows better what to teach and how than we do... teachers here must be more competent than in Bangladesh so we do not worry...”(Male, International student)

Also education policies in some countries emphasise parental participation whereas in others it is considerably less emphasised. For instance, in the National Education Policy of Bangladesh (MoE, 2010) there is no explicit emphasis on parental involvement in their children’s schooling. It only mentions the need to raise awareness about children’s education ‘through the establishment of pro-active guardians-teachers committees’ (MoE, 2010, p. 8). The scenario was even worse before. This cultural background has influence on shaping the views of Bangladeshi migrant parents in terms of parental participation in the schools.

One respondent said,

“It is school’s duty to teach the children. Our parents did not worry much about our schooling when we were studying. The school did not bothered them much. Similarly, . we cannot do anything worrying about it (children’s schooling)...” (Female, House wife)

1.5 Socio-economic status

Socio-economic status had a strong influence on respondents’ views about their relationship with children’s schooling. Among them, male respondents were more explicit in this regard. In some cases parents show interest about choosing schools but for economic limitations they are not able to do so. Occupations of the respondents are included here to indicate their socio-economic status.

‘I could not afford to send my daughter to a school which have 80 percent British teacher’ (Male, Businessman)

‘In Newham, there is no grammar school. There is some grammar school in Redbridge. However, we could not move our house just for a good school...’ (Male, Lecturer)

Respondents in this study also tended to relate their socio-economic status with the nature of their involvement which has shaped their decision on the different aspects of children’s education. Respondents in this study also viewed their children’s education positively despite socio-economic barriers. Similarly, Miller, Cable and Devereux (2005) identified that irrespective of family’s cultural, social, religious or economic background, parents try their best to support their children’s intellectual and social development.

2. School Factors

2.1 Parent’s trust on school and teacher

Data shows that a majority of respondents showed a deep sense of trust in schools and teachers. Number of respondents indicated that they are sure what are the schools doing must be useful for their children. Moreover, they consider schools in England are much better than those in their home country. Teachers are believed as highly competent thus some of the respondents believe that it is not always necessary to interfere into the school activities for the parents. One of the respondents said,

'There is no unqualified teacher in any schools. All the schools maintain a minimum standard when it comes to staffing...'

Another suggested, (Male, Lecturer)

'I like their [schools'] every measure... They are way better than how I had thought. How they help me is unbelievable. It is encouraging... We really rely on them. Teachers are very intimate, they take the responsibility, they take care of them. Also my daughter loves them so much; sometimes I think she loves them more than us' (Male, Businessman)

This trust might be because of the new context of the school for the parents who are used to with the schools in Bangladesh. Since, they are from a developing country and now resided in a developed one, things are resembled as standard. That type of trust and believe of parent's might be a relief for the teachers and schools however, parent's active participation and critical thinking about the teacher and school is important. Although DfES (2007) asserted that schools are effective in working with parents and recognising the difference between parents who have different needs; De Carvalho (2001) also pointed out that parent involvement is often controlled by the school.

Nevertheless, a few respondents showed high expectation from the schools..

'In the parent meeting held once in every three months where they give me a report. If they can arrange this meeting once in two weeks or once a month, then it would be easier for me to know more about his progress... ' (Female, Catering worker)

'It is my duty to look after him at home and it is his [teacher's] duty to look after him in the school. If he has any problem, then teachers have to find it why and solve it' (Female, Shoe outlet worker)

In addition to that, parents of this study mentioned their expectations from schools and teachers; however, how schools responded to those expectations is a matter of concern. Only two respondents discussed getting responses as per their expectations.

However, this should not be the case and more parents should be able to elicit expected responses. As Bastiani (2003, p. 18) pointed out -

'All parents want to be taken seriously – to have a say and be listened to, to feel part of the school and to know that they matter'

2.2 Communication

Watkins (1997) found that parent-teacher communication as measured by parental reporting is one of the significant predictors of parents' involvement in a primary school setting. In this study parents indicated their interest about this type of communication. Most of them talked about their strong belief in its importance. An easy communication was expected from both sides of the parent-school relationship.

'If I have a good relationship with you, then I could ask for help or assistance in understanding something. So school and parent relationship should be such that neither side hesitate to contact with the other' (Male, Lecturer)

However, they also mentioned that due to their job schedule they often fail to maintain such communication since most of them are involved in jobs that have unorthodox timing (based on different shifts).

Nevertheless, a strong belief in teachers and schools emerged from the respondents' narrative that is likely to encourage teacher-parent communication.

Respondents also see it as a helpful way to involve themselves with the school and the teacher.

3. Policy factors

Although there are quite a few policy documents that emphasize on school-parent partnership, very few specific action points are found in them. Moreover, parents are considered to be homogeneous (in terms of their background) in those documents and needs of minority parents with different backgrounds have been acknowledged in very few areas.

This study found that the Bangladeshi migrant parents feel themselves of no use in the parents meeting since they hardly can communicate with parents who speaks different languages.. In several cases the respondents pointed out that in the parents meeting they just sit inactively and listen to the teachers or receive the progress reports. The teachers treated all parents similarly.

Government policies started prioritising Home-School which first emphasised the parents' role 'as a source of potential educational benefit' (Hood, 1999, p. 430). It also explained that parental involvement in their children's education was an important element of effective education (DES, 1967). This involvement included home-based parental participation, such as, listening to children read and supervision of homework and school-based parental involvement, such as, attending parent education workshops and parent-teacher meetings.

Moreover, in 1997, the Government White Paper 'Excellence in Schools' was established to secure parental participation, where three elements in the Government's strategy were emphasised:, providing parents with information, giving parents a voice, and encouraging parental partnerships with schools (Desforges and Abouchar, 2003).

Then in 1998, the 'Home-School Agreement' was introduced to provide a framework for the development of home-school collaboration. It was argued that as parents are recognized as children's first educators; when Parents and Schools work together, children can learn more effectively as parents can help more effectively (DfEE, 1998a). Parents are considered as the one who knows their children comparing better than others and wishing best for them (DCSF, 2009b). So the rationale behind the agreement is that by giving parents' voice, their quality participation in children's education can be ensured.

In contrary to what the policies suggest, in England, parents have limited powers in reality, though they are encouraged to become more involved. According to Hood (1999), one of the most crucial criticisms of policy regarding parental participation is that, in practice, inequalities and differences between parents themselves have been ignored by the policy rhetoric. Moreover, Hood (2001) found limited evidence of promoting partnership between parents and schools. The power difference between parents and schools is largely ignored and parents are often considered a homogeneous group neglecting significant factors such as race, class, and gender.

Despite parents being acknowledged as important contributors in children's attainment and achievement (Desforges and Abouchar, 2003), these policies did not include specific attention to ways of promoting involvement of minority parents.

This is also reflected in the 1985 ILEA Survey of Bangladeshi mothers in Tower Hamlets where positive attitudes towards educational provisions were found. In addition, DCSF (2009) reported that Asian parents have placed 'an extremely high importance on the value of education', though Hutchison and Varlaam (1985) found fewer strategies for Home-School communication.

Conclusion

Several research findings and government documents have acknowledged the importance of parent's participation in their children's learning in home and school. Different policy documents and many British schools are promoting parent's participation. However, only emphasising this issue generally is not enough specially in a very diversely populated area like England or more specifically London. Migrant parents who have very different educational and cultural background need special attention, which is overlooked almost all the times. Migrant parents like Bangladeshi migrants experience number of obstacles in participating their children's learning specially participating with school.

This study found several barriers experienced by Bangladeshi migrant parents and clustered those into three main areas namely; parent factors, school factors and policy factors. It argued that due to struggle for establishment in new country, lack of knowledge and understandings about new education system and proper language skill, different cultural background, existing socio-economic status as an immigrant parents are less likely to participate actively in school activities. Apart from that, the image of school to the parents and communication with the school faculties also seems as barrier, argued by this study. Moreover, the policy documents refer parents as homogeneous group and the schools acts so. Hence, migrant parent's special demands of support are overlooked. This research was very limited in scope and for better understanding, future researches might want to focus on these areas with more emphasis and gather more detailed information.

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